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ABSTRACT

The initiative to design and build a high efficiency klystron to be used in the LHC as a demonstrator was launched in 2018. Simulation packages developed at CERN predicted a beam to RF power efficiency of 70% for a new optimized CERN design, using the same power converter and infrastructure in use in the LHC. A collaboration with THALES (FR), the manufacturer of the original klystron was established to convert one unit that is currently in use in LHC into a high-efficiency model, while reusing most of the ancillary systems like the solenoid, support frame, output coaxial to waveguide transition gun. The new model is fully compatible with the installation at CERN without major modifications, so it can be used as a spare for the LHC machine.

The final performance of the tube allows for a higher RF power generated from the same power consumption. This opens the possibility to use it for the high luminosity upgrade of the current LHC

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

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Executive summary

The initiative to design and build a high efficiency klystron to be used in the LHC as a demonstrator was launched in 2018. Simulation packages developed at CERN predicted a beam to RF power efficiency of 70% for a new optimized CERN design, using the same power converter and infrastructure in use in the LHC. A collaboration with THALES (FR), the manufacturer of the original klystron was established to convert one unit that is currently in use in LHC into a high-efficiency model, while reusing most of the ancillary systems like the solenoid, support frame, output coaxial to waveguide transition gun. The new model is fully compatible with the installation at CERN without major modifications, so it can be used as a spare for the LHC machine.

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1 Introduction

The RF cavities of the LHC ring at CERN have been powered with sixteen TH2167 klystrons delivering each 300kW CW at 400MHz. For the next LHC Hi-Lumi operation, there is a need for higher RF power sources.

The overall project includes the upgrade of the CERN TH2167 sockets with the goal of reaching 350kW saturated output power whilst keeping the same operating point (58kV x 9A) to preserve the present power supplies. That means increasing the klystron efficiency to the level of 67-68% compared to the 60-62% present value. The new design should also allow the plug-in replacement of existing tubes.

The technical approach is to implement an interaction structure studied by CERN with 1.5D klystron computer code KlyC. The ‘Core Stabilization Method’ (CSM) has been applied to define a shorter six cavities structure including a second and a third harmonic cavities with 70-72% predicted efficiency. The most economical scenario is to re-design the interaction structure and to re-use some subassemblies as the solenoid, the air gun tank, the coax to waveguide transition and the supporting frame.

The following Table 1 summarizes and compares the main specifications of the existing TH2167 with the target specification of the upgraded TH2167HE.

Table 1: main parameters of the original tube and the upgraded version design for high efficiency.

	TH2167	TH2167HE
Power [kW]	300	350
Frequency [MHz]	400.8	400.8
Gun microPerveance	1.65	1.65
Beam microPerveance	0.7	0.7
Cathode voltage [kV]	58	58
Anode Voltage [kV]	≤35	≤35
Beam current [A]	8.5	9
Efficiency [%]	60	≥65
Gain [dB]	≥37	≥37
Bandwidth [MHz]	±1	±0.7
Group delay [ns]	130	≤250

2 Design and simulations

The TH2167 and the new TH2167HE are composed of:

- the air tank fitted with the three HV connectors (from Pantak)
- the klystron body, including the gun, the cavities, the collector, the RF window, and the housing parts (boiler, ion pump magnet, connectors...),
- the electromagnet,
- the coax to WR2300 HH waveguide transition,
- the supporting frame equipped with lifting eye bolts and wheels

The main design modifications implemented in the new TH2167 HE are the following items:

- a new interaction structure using six cavities, including a second and third harmonic cavities
- the cavities assembly technology
- the tuning system of some cavities,
- a new collector allowing more margin on power dissipation
- other items like the electromagnet and the supporting frame have been slightly modified

2.1 INTERACTION STRUCTURE

Prior to the start of the project, CERN carried out several studies to define a HE interaction structure. Recurrent exchanges between CERN and THALES teams have enabled us to integrate the geometries and characteristics of the reused subsets and to take into account the various mechanical architectural constraints identified on the 3D model.

The structures explored by CERN were defined thanks to a powerful optimization module integrated in KlyC (klystron code 1.5 D).

The interaction structure has 6 cavities with the 3rd one operating close to the second harmonic and the 4th one operating close to the third harmonic. The addition of the third harmonic cavity improves the electrons bunching and therefore increases efficiency.

Following the start of the project, interaction calculations were continued with KlyC and Klys2D codes. After several exchanges regarding the bandwidth specifications, the frequencies of the cavities were reviewed in order to satisfy LHC low level RF system requirements. Once calculated with Klys2D, we obtain the results presented in increase the efficiency at saturation by approximately 7 points. We see that there is a very low level of reflected electrons below saturation for both structures, which is acceptable. However, by decreasing the magnetic field in the last two coils, it is observed with Klys2D that the reflected electrons are nearly eliminated. As expected, the efficiency increases slightly by approximately one point. Even though the simulations results diverge, the reflected electron current and power values are close enough to approve the coils design. By powering the last two coils separately, we will be able to study the impact of the magnetic field on the output signal during high power testing..

Figure 1: Pictures showing the beam bunching along the two interaction structures; Klys2D

Nevertheless, the calculations carried out by CERN with PIC solver simulations, have shown that by decreasing the magnetic field in the last two coils by 20%, the current (and power) of the reflected electrons increases, from 290 μ A (6.8W) to 2.65mA (58.7W). These current values remain low enough to validate this design. The simulations, in both cases, are stable, which means the reflected electrons don't generate parasitic side bands, at least at a significant level.

Figure 2 Final performance expected by the new tube in terms of body interception and reflected electrons

Another parameter to which particular attention has been paid is the bandwidth at -1dB of saturated power. As indicated in the TH2167 specification, the bandwidth at -1dB shall be greater than or equal to ± 1 MHz.

Figure 3: Bandwidths at saturation (blue curves) and 1dB below saturation (green curves).

The figures above compare the bandwidth of the TH2167 and the TH2167HE. It can be seen that the 3rd harmonic cavity significantly reduces the bandwidth at the bottom of the band. However, after a few adjustments we obtain with the HE structure a bandwidth greater than ± 0.7 MHz at Psat-1dB, which has been validated by CERN. This was achieved by decreasing the cavities frequencies by several hundred kHz.

The beam channel was carefully assessed for the risk of monotron oscillations and multipacting. Tolerance studies and the corresponding tuning strategy were also analysed in detail by Thales as part of the design process.

2.2 BEAM FOCUSING SOLENOID

In order to match with the new interaction structure, the design of the solenoid has to be lightly modified. Therefore, the coils # 6, 7 and 14 have been displaced along the gun direction by 20, 35

and 7mm respectively. Comparing the axial magnetic field calculated in each case, we note that the differences are lower than 20 gauss in the vicinity of displaced coils.

During interaction calculations, we found that the new HE structure requires a higher magnetic field level than a standard structure. This implies higher solenoid current. Excessive current can significantly increase the temperature of the coils and damage them. Experiments have been conducted to define the nominal current (10.5 A) that we are allowed to apply. For adjustment purposes, the terminal block of the solenoid must be modified to allow the use of two power supplies. The objective is to set the last two coils current separately.

2.3 COLLECTOR

The average power density deposited on the inner wall of the collector expected from simulations is plotted on Figure 4. Depending on the magnetic field applied, the power density in the cylindrical part is close to or even exceeds the limit value (500 W/cm²) defined in Thales design rules.

Figure 4: Average power density on the collector inner wall (top) The collectors' geometries of the TH2167 (a) and the TH2167HE (bottom)

There is thus a decrease in intercepted power density of 18%. Therefore, this new collector presents larger safety margin with regard to thermal loading.

3 Manufacturing

3.1 THE PUMPED TUBE

The 3D models of the TH2167 klystron and the TH2167HE klystron are shown in Figure 5 below. The TH2167HE klystron consists of nine main sub-assemblies:

- HV gun including cathode, cathode stem and two HV ceramic seal
- input cavity, n°1
- cavity n°2
- second harmonic cavity, n°3
- third harmonic cavity, n°4
- cavity n°5 and the output cavity n°6
- the coaxial window and 2 vac-ion pumps
- collector

Figure 48 : Pumped TH2167 klystron view

Figure 49 : Pumped TH2167 HE klystron view

Figure 5: View of Pumped tube TH2167 (left) klystron view and the new high efficiency counterpart TH2167 HE (right)

The ion pumps, the RF window as well as the HV gun do not change compared to the existing TH2167 klystron. All the cavities remain made of copper. The architecture of cavities 1, 2 and penultimate

change, the spun copper cavities have been replaced by machined cylindrical cavities. This facilitates machining and compliance of manufacturing tolerances. The drifts are all water-cooled. The cooling principle has been taken from TH2167: the hydraulic connection between two drifts is made with copper pipes and flexible pipes. Cavities n° 1, 2 and 5 are tuned tanks to axial gap variation. The other cavities are tuned by a radial tuning system which can allow two adjustments: a coarse adjustment by playing on the depression of the system in the cavity before brazing, then a second finer adjustment by playing on the deformation of the membrane.

The klystron is assembled vertically, collector down. At each assembly step the sub-assemblies are aligned and welded. After the final vacuum leak test, the klystron is lifted and positioned in the same orientation into the baking oven.

The sub-assembly consisting of the last two cavities and the window is the most critical to manufacture, it is assembled by means of seven intermediate brazing. To secure the manufacture of this sub-assembly, a test vehicle was carried out ahead of time. After each intermediate brazing, visual inspections and leak tests were carried out systematically. This test vehicle allowed the validation of the tuning system.

The different assemblies under manufacture but before final assembly are shown in Figure 6. A view of the old TH2167 next to the high efficiency version can be in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Part assemblies for the TH2167HE tube prototype

TH2167

TH2167HE

Figure 7: Final view of the pumped tube for the old and new version of the TH2167 klystron

3.2 THE HOUSED TUBE

The housing parts will largely be taken from the TH2167. Some of these parts will be replaced (boiler) or modified (electromagnet and frame) will be modified to be compatible with the new design of the pumped tube. We took advantage of this redesign work to first evaluate the conformity of the configuration of our product with the applicable European directives and then secondly to make some mainly electrical design modifications which are in line with these directives.

Electrical interface

The ground circuitry has been redesigned to respond to the applicable standard NF EN 61010-1. One main ground interface is placed on the bottom part of the frame. The Protective Earth terminal marked PE (M8 threaded rod) is used for connection of external protective conductor. The pumped tube, electromagnet, air tank, and frame linked to the ground with protective bonding (Green and yellow cables). The electromagnet is equipped with its own grounding interface. This secondary interface is connected both to the main ground distribution platina and also to the different electromagnet sub-assemblies. Current feedback is designed by CERN for TH2167 and it is integrated in the definition file of the TH2167HE. The interface is a M16 threaded rod linked to de pumped tube by a bent copper bar.

Figure 8: Main ground interface

The Solenoid SOCAPEX power connector have been replaced by Harting's HAN Q2 connector. This connector is used by Thales on other klystron references. It meets the latest standards and is equipped with coding pins (pin 1 and 2) allowing the two connectors to be differentiated and avoiding human errors. They are equipped with a ground terminal which is connected to the electromagnet ground circuit.

RF interface

The definition file has been updated to take into account the new position of the RF input interface defined by CERN. The RF interface is placed at a middle high on the electromagnet, on the same side as the output window. The N type connector is the same as TH2167 (RADIALL R 161 270).

Figure 9: RF interface as installed in the housed tube

Hydraulic interface

The body cooling I/O interfaces remain unchanged. The housed klystron is transported in a horizontal position then tilted to a vertical position (operating position). Due to the increased length of the collector, the hydraulic interfaces are closer to the ground during tilting and the risk of interference has increased. In order to limit this risk, the solution agreed with CERN is to reduce the length of the water inlet and outlet pipes of the boiler. This provides sufficient clearance from the ground. In addition, the 3D representation and the 2D plan of the connection tube have been updated based on the dimensions provided by CERN.

Frame

A frame designed for safe shipment in horizontal position and safe handling in both positions mechanically supports the assembly including the electromagnet, air tank and the klystron. Structural calculations allowed to check the suitability of the frame to support the new HE klystron. The mass of the different subassemblies estimated from the 3D model is 1538 kg. Considering margins and security coefficient of 1.5, the final mass used in the calculation is 2642 kg.

Structural calculations have been done for all static, lifting and rotating configurations shown on this paragraph. For rotation and horizontal lifting, the calculation has been made without the removable shielding and grids. The main structure is over dimensioned. The screws fixing the different parts of the frame are strong enough. The areas of fixation of the lifting rings have a lower security margin but it is sufficient. The VLBG lifting rings with double rotation must be used. The rotation procedure must be done slowly to limit the acceleration.

The recommended minimum chains angles and length for the different lifting configuration are shown below. The shielding and grids must be only placed only when the Klystron is vertical.

X-ray shielding

The radiation protection standard has more restrictive since the design and construction of the original klystron TH2167. The maximum level, of tolerated X-ray dose rate, was decreased from $5\mu\text{Sv/h}$ at 1 m from the klystron to $1\mu\text{Sv/h}$ at 10 cm from any accessible surface. To meet this new requirement, the X-ray shielding was modified with the addition of shielding panels with lead. Grids and cover were also added to prevent access to X-ray leaking areas. The collector shielding is made of lead strip 4mm thickness assembled around it. Shielded panels with 2 mm lead are placed on the first half of the klystron. The top of the shielding is around 2m high. Grids protect the remaining part of the klystron.

The grids and the shielding plates are hanged to the frame with bended parts and assembled by angled brackets. Handles have been added to facilitate handling. These grids will have an opening percentage of approximately 80% to allow the evacuation of heat coming from the electromagnet.

Figure 10: View of the removable shielding and grids

The original klystron sent by CERN was the first unit of the model and the accompanying frame was found to be significantly different making difficult some of the proposed modifications. It was decided jointly by Thales and CERN to re-use the frame of a later unit identical to most of the other klystrons and compatible with the new design. The final klystron was fully assembled by July 2024 when it was installed in the test bench at Thales. It can be seen in at his testing position in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Final housed tube in testing position at Thale.

4 Final measurements

The test campaign at Thales started in July 2024 by pulsing high voltage with increasingly longer duty cycle until CW operation at nominal beam power of 547kW measured by calorimetry. After applying RF, signs of multipacting were seen on the output coaxial. Copper parts in the window assembly turned blue and temperature increase was observed even at lower input power. A degradation of the power was seen at lower input power.

Also, the power extracted from the tube was significantly lower than the predicted value. Simulations by CERN indicated that a detuning of the second harmonic cavity could be the origin of the problem. The required retuning of the cavity was beyond the capability of the tuning system, so it was decided to adjust the distance between the two plates positioned on either side of the cavity to allow it to deform slightly. After this was done, the original performance was reestablished.

Calculations made at CERN, indicated also that positioning permanent magnets around the window enclosure could improve the multipacting. Thales positioned permanent magnets and verified that the multipacting was now relegated to very small input power outside the operating range of the tube.

During the factory test in September where a CERN team visited the Thales factory, the tube demonstrated a maximum power of about 365kW with an enhanced efficiency of 70% as per design (see Figure 12)

Figure 12: Power-meter measurement of the input and output power for the klystron. Output power reached 364.8 KW at CW well above the required 350 kW.

Some sidebands were observed in the output signal as can be seen in Figure 13. Retuning cavity 5 using the built-in tuning system move the side-bands beyond saturation. On the other hand, this reduced the efficiency for the 200 kW mode. Ultimately, the solution chosen to eliminate the parasitic lines was to adjust the current of the coils. We set the current of the main coils and the last two coils on the output cavity side to 9.4 A and 11.3 A, respectively, instead of 10.5 A for all the coils as calculated.

Figure 13: View of the sidebands observed during testing (top) and after adjustments of the cavity 5.

The final efficiency of the klystron along the operating load line can be seen in Figure 14. After the different tuning errors and re-tuning procedures were implemented in the design file of the tube, the agreement between measurements and simulations is extremely good. It can be considered a digital twin of the tube on which measurements can now be tested against. The measured data for the bandwidth in Figure 15 is one example of the use of this digital twin. The measurement data shows an excellent agreement with the simulation.

Figure 14: Measured efficiency of the TH2167HE tube (orange empty dots) against the expected values as simulated by KlyC and Klys2Dcodes. The agreement with KlyC was reached after modifications of the cavity 5 frequency as expected from the tuning at Thales.

Figure 15: Measurements of the power at saturation for different frequencies together with expected value according to KlyC simulations.

Measurements of the power and efficiency at operating points different from the nominal were also done (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Power and efficiency measured and simulated at different operating points for klystron TH2167HE.

The prototype arrived at CERN on October 30, 2024, and is currently connected to the test bench waiting for final validation tests before launching the construction of the remaining units necessary to run HL-LHC.

5 Future plans / Conclusion / relation to other IFAST work

Initially aimed at being a proof of principle, it became apparent during the project that the new beam parameters expected from the high luminosity LHC upgrade will benefit from a higher power per klystron. The high-efficiency model is indeed able to produce 350 kW instead of 300 by using the same electrical power. It can be installed in the LHC cavern with minimal modifications.

While shortcomings were observed during test like multipacting and a detuning of the 2nd harmonic cavity, this should be corrected on the next units and do not represent a mayor difficulty. Excessive heating of the harmonic cavities was also observed. Additional cooling should be implemented on the next units.

Based on the successful construction and results of the TH2167HE klystron, CERN is investigating the possibility to substitute most of the existing klystrons of LHC for their high efficiency version allowing for an increase of the available power during the HL-LHC era. Commercial discussions should take place during 2025 for an expected start of construction in 2026.

6 References

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